

Varietal reaction to rice tungro disease in deepwater transplanted variety trials at Pusa, Bihar, India

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Rice tungro virus symptoms were noticed in August 1980 in two varieties, Bhutahi and BR46, in a transplanted deepwater variety trial, UVT-6 (State). The population of green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*, the tungro vector, increased and the disease spread fast. Tungro symptoms appeared in many varieties. Infection started with the yellowing of leaves. Later, plants were

Reaction of rice varieties to tungro virus.

Score	Entries (no.)	Varieties, lines
1	1	Jaladhi-1
3	6	Janaki (64-117), NC 487/77, CN 603, C 188-1, BIET 820, C 62-10.
5	5	OR 1103, C 185-1, C180-4, C 62-31, C 183-1.
7	11	RAU 21-35-3-5, (BIET 821), RAU 21-82-1-3 (BIET 799), RAU 21-147-1-4 (BIET 807), KLG 70-P, OR 1105, BR 14, CN 540, Pichar, C 181-1, C 186-1, BIET 821.
9	9	RAU 21-168-1-2 (BIET 724), C 62-68, Bhutahi, Bajal. Jalaj. KLG 165-P, KLG 161-7-P, BR 46, OR 1104.

stunted. The disease was first noticed in the center of the plot; it later spread to other parts.

UVT-6 (All-India Coordinated Rice

Improvement Program), a transplanted deepwater variety trial in the adjacent plot, also showed the disease symptoms. Both the UVT-6 (State) and UVT-6 (AICRIP) trials had three replications. Scoring was based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (1976) and the maximum score was used for varietal reaction (see table). Of 32 entries from 2 trials, only 7 had resistant reactions. The direct-seeded trial in the adjacent field had very little damage.

Janaki (64-117), released in 1980 for cultivation in deepwater areas (up to 150 cm water depth) of North Bihar, is resistant to tungro. So, it replaces BR14 and BR46, the earlier released varieties for similar situations. The nature of the disease was confirmed by rice virologists at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. ■

Multiple disease resistance breeding materials in Karnataka

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The following cultivars were evaluated under field pressure during the 1979 kharif at the RRS, V. C. Farm, and found resistant to discoloration and ephelis, leaf and neck blast, and brown spot fungal diseases. The cultivars represent a relatively wide genetic base and will be good donors in breeding programs.

RP1045-714-3-3 (IET 6884), TR1-15 (IET 7054), RNR 87893 (IET 7063),

KAU1674 (IET 7096), CR260-501-294-51 (IET 7144), CR263-889 (IET 7145), RP1153-12-4 (IET 6627), RP1045-23-2-1 (IET 6314), RP1017-1-5-1 (IET 6664), Raminad Str. 3, Usen, IR1721-11-5-3-2-3-1, Milyang 30, IR1544-38-2-2, IR32, BR167-2B-9 (Asha), H 5, IR1905-PP11-29-4-61, IR2588-5-1-2, IR2797-105-2-2-3, IR5853-162-1-2-3, IR8608-82-1-3-1-3, IR10198-662, IR13429-198-2, Rasht 507, 5721. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Studies on varietal resistance and host specificity of rice green leafhoppers

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Because the green leafhoppers (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) and *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stal) are important pests of rice, detailed investigations of insect-plant relationships were undertaken.

A high degree of resistance was sought among 108 known pest-resistant

entries. In host-plant preference tests, 76 and 72 entries had significantly less damage from *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus*. In general, *N. nigropictus* caused more damage than *N. virescens* to the same varieties. In various tests, PTB 2, PTB 18, and PTB 7 were highly resistant, and Khama 49/ 8, PTB 21, DS 1, ARC 6049, Khama 49/2, ARC 10243, and Jhinga sail were resistant to both species. The adult longevity test was found to be a good criterion for identifying high levels of resistance in rice varieties.

The high level of resistance of PTB 2, PTB 18, and PTB 7 could be due to the fact that both GLH species showed a

low preference for settling and egg-laying on those varieties. Both leafhopper species preferred to settle and oviposit on 30- to 40-day-old plants.

A high level of antibiosis was observed on PTB-2, PTB 18, and PTB 7. Those varieties caused high mortality of first-instar nymphs and newly emerged adults caged on them. There was also low damage to 15-day-old seedlings on which 100 nymphs were caged for 20 days. Plant age did not alter the degree of antibiosis. Insects of both species made more feeding punctures and excreted less honeydew during feeding on resistant varieties. Analysis of the plant tissue demonstrated successful

insertion of insect stylets into the feeding sites and indicate that mechanical barriers were not involved in varietal resistance.

Host range studies involving 56 plant species indicated that *N. virescens* can survive and breed only on rice, while *N. nigropictus* has a host range that includes rice, sugarcane, and five graminaceous weeds. *N. nigropictus* showed greater preference for *Leersia hexandra* than for any other plant including TN1 rice. However, both species could lay eggs even on nonhosts. *N. virescens* made more feeding marks and excreted less honeydew when caged on the host plants suited to *N. nigropictus*, suggest-

ing that narrow host specificity may be due to an imbalance in phagostimulants or the presence of phagodeterrents.

These results show that chemosensory, particularly gustatory, stimuli play an important role in host selection in green leafhoppers.

The biochemical causes of resistance to leafhoppers in rice were also investigated. The total phenol content of resistant varieties was relatively higher than that of the susceptible TN1, but it was also high in *L. hexandra*. Thus, individual phenolic compounds may play a role in susceptibility or resistance.

The role of amino acids was not clear because their concentration was low

both in resistant rice varieties and in *L. hexandra*, which was the most suitable host for *N. nigropictus*.

Feeding stimulation and inhibition by various chemicals and plant extracts of resistant and susceptible varieties were bioassayed. Sucrose was highly stimulatory and a few amino acids slightly stimulated feeding. Amino acid derivatives, organic acids, and phenolic compounds were strongly deterrent. Similarly, both GLH species had low preference for chloroform and acetone extracts of resistant varieties, but similar extracts from susceptible plants were readily accepted. ■

Varietal resistance of rice to leaf folder

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A trial was conducted through the upland rice varietal screening program to select varieties suitable for dryland paddy cultivation in the hilly zone of Karnataka in 1980 kharif. Twenty-one entries were included in this trial, replicated three times. During the trial, incidence of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* was severe, but some varieties were observed to have lower levels of damage. The damage on different varieties was recorded (see table). ARC25, KMP133, and KMP58 had minimum damage and were also moderately resistant to blast. ■

Extent of damage^a by leaf folder in different rice varieties. Karnataka, India.

Entry	Leaf damage (%)
Kala keni	69.4
CR222-MW-10	65.5
ARC25	10.6
Black Gora	69.0
Bala	100.0
IR6115-1-1-1	100.0
OR165-85-12	66.9
KMP39	47.2
KMP(A) 57	75.0
OR165-28-14B	51.2
OR165-18-8	100.0
CRM13-3241	100.0
N22	42.4
MR262	75.0
CR143-2-2	100.0
CR245-1	100.0
KMP58	28.7
IET1444	96.7
KMP133	11.8
KMP134	39.4
Jaya	71.8

^aAv of 3 replications.

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Selection pathways for dryland rice breeding

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Progenies of two rice crosses — IR3135 (IR1539-823-1-4/IR1917-3-17) and

IR3189 (IR1721-11-13-20-1-2/C4-63) — were grown and selected under wetland and dryland conditions. The result was three different selection pathways. The pathways (F₂ and F₃) were: 1 = dryland/dryland; 2 = wetland/dryland; and 3 = wetland/wetland lines. F₄ from the two crosses and three pathways were compared under dryland conditions for grain yield and yield components.

The pathways affected neither the grain yield nor the yield components. The two crosses differed significantly in 100-grain weight, tiller number, and plant height, but did not differ significantly in grain yield, panicle number, or panicle length. The variables studied showed no significant interactions.

Statistically nonsignificant mean squares and relatively small variance